

Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) Complexes with Phenyl Urea

P. K. PANDA and B. K. MOHAPATRA

Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack-753 003

Manuscript received 9 August 1979, accepted 30 December 1979

A number of complexes having the general formula ML_2X_2 is described in which $M^{+2} = Co, Ni, Cu$ and Zn , "L" stands for phenyl urea and $X = Cl^-, Br^-$ or NO_3^- . These are characterised on the basis of analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infrared and electronic spectral data.

AMONG the ligands having a C=O group as the donor site, the amides and lactams are particularly interesting since these molecules possess also an amine group, which potentially may (also) act as a donor to the metal ion. However, with transition metal ions thus far only compounds have been isolated that contain oxygen co-ordinated lactams and amides. Earlier we have studied¹⁻³ the complexes of some lactams, dicyanadiamide and acrylamide. Introducing a second amine group in the ligand at the other side of the C=O group produces another type of ligands. This

class of ligands is also very interesting, since now three possible bonding sites are present which may yield several type of complexes e.g. monodentate via either oxygen or nitrogen, bridging bidentate via oxygen and nitrogen or bridging bidentate via two nitrogen atoms. In addition, hydrogen bonds with the anions may occur even when co-ordination via one nitrogen occurs. It was therefore thought worthwhile to study the complexation behaviour of phenyl urea with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) ions.

Experimental

All the chemicals used are of AnalaR grade. Ethanolic solution of metal salts was treated with ethanolic solution of phenyl urea in (1:2) molar proportion and it was refluxed for one hour. Resulting clear solution was kept overnight, when crystalline compounds were separated out. These were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol followed by ether

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compounds	M.P. (°C)	ΔM (mhos. cm ²)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	% of metal		% of nitrogen	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1. Co L ₂ Cl ₂	148	5.6	5.0	14.24	14.66	6.42	6.96
2. Co L ₂ Br ₂	140	5.8	5.2	11.86	12.03	5.34	5.71
3. Co L ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	145	6.4	5.2	12.45	12.95	11.98	12.31
4. Ni L ₂ Cl ₂	202	5.5	3.0	14.26	14.61	6.51	6.97
5. Ni L ₂ Br ₂	195	7.8	3.0	11.58	11.99	5.32	5.71
6. Ni L ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	140	8.2	3.3	12.56	12.91	11.82	12.31
7. Cu L ₂ Cl ₂	105	6.4	1.8	15.28	15.62	6.35	6.88
8. Cu L ₂ Br ₂	155	6.8	1.84	12.47	12.85	5.12	5.66
9. Cu L ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	165	7.5	1.82	13.51	13.82	11.86	12.18
10. Zn L ₂ Cl ₂	185	8.2	—	15.82	16.00	6.35	6.85
11. Zn L ₂ Br ₂	178	8.4	—	12.82	13.17	5.26	5.64
12. Zn L ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	186	7.8	—	13.85	14.17	11.86	12.13

L = Phenyl Urea.

TABLE 2—INFRARED AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRA cm^{-1}

Com- pound No.	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$	ν_{max} in k.k.(ϵ)
Ligand	1670	3400	—	—	—
1	1660	3380, 3290	455	260	19.0(45), 8.4(15)
2	1660	3390, 3290	450	260	19.2(45), 8.5(15)
3	1660	3380, 3300	445	265	19.0(40), 8.4(15)
4	1655	3390, 3280	450	255	9.0(5), 14.7(6), 24.5(16)
5	1650	3380, 3290	450	265	9.0(5), 14.9(6), 24.8(16)
6	1650	3390, 3300	455	270	9.0(5), 15.1(6), 24.8(16)
7	1665	3390, 3280	445	275	13.8(35)
8	1660	3375, 3270	450	265	14.0(38)
9	1660	3380, 3280	455	260	14.3(40)
10	1655	3390, 3280	425	280	—
11	1655	3390, 3300	430	275	—
12	1660	3380, 3290	430	280	—

and dried in vacuum desiccator. Metal in the complexes was estimated by E.D.T.A titration methods, nitrogen by micro analysis and conductance was measured in $M/1000$ acetone solution of the complexes using Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility were measured by Gouy method. Infrared spectra were recorded in KBr phase using Beckman I.R. -20 and I.R. -12 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded in $M/100$ (chloroform-ligand) solutions using Hilger watt uvispeck spectrophotometer. Relevant data are presented in Table 1 and Table 2.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes have the general formula ML_2X_2 where $\text{M}^{+2} = \text{Co}, \text{Ni}, \text{Cu}$ and Zn , $\text{L} = \text{Phenyl urea}$ and X is anion $= \text{Cl}^-$ or Br^- or NO_3^- . These have relatively low melting points and are fairly soluble in acetone in which the molar conductance values are low indicating non-electrolytic nature. Magnetic moment of the complexes are in the range of 5.0 - 5.2, 3.0 - 3.3 and 1.8 - 1.84 B.M. for cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes respectively indicating a spin free octahedral or distorted octahedral configuration.

All the cobalt(II) complexes are pink crystalline solids nickel(II) compounds are light green and copper(II) complexes are green solids.

Infrared spectra in the amide region have been frequently used for distinguishing between -O and -N co-ordination. $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ (amide-I band) usually occurs⁴ in the 1650-1690 cm^{-1} region. In the ligand this has been observed at 1670 cm^{-1} and in the complexes this band was found $\sim 1660 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating⁵ co-ordination through the oxygen atom. Amide-II

band is observed at 1620 cm^{-1} in the ligand and $\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes. Further in the ligand $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ occurred at 3400 cm^{-1} which splits and observed at a lower frequency region in the complexes ~ 3380 and 3290 cm^{-1} . Lowering may partly be due to hydrogen bonding with the anion. But from the consideration of the position and nature of $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ and amide-II band, bonding through the nitrogen of the-NH group is also expected. This has been further supported⁶ by the observation of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ 420-450 and 250-280 cm^{-1} regions in the far infrared spectra in agreement with earlier observation⁷. In case of nitrate complexes $\Delta\nu$ (difference between ν_4 and ν_1 bands on co-ordination due to splitting of the ν_8 mode of ionic nitrate group) is of the order of $\sim 130 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating⁸ monodentate nitrate co-ordination.

The electronic spectra of cobalt(II) complexes in solution show two absorption bands ~ 19.0 (45) and 8.4 (15) k.k. regions attributable⁹ to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$ transitions respectively. A spin free octahedral configuration is suggested for these complexes in conformity with magnetic moment data. Nickel(II) complexes give rise to three weak absorption bands ~ 9.0 (5), 14.7 - 15.1 (6) and 24.5 - 24.8 (16; k.k. regions assignable¹⁰ to ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}$, \rightarrow

${}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ transitions respectively and a spin free octahedral stereochemistry is presumed for these compounds basing on μ_{eff} values. In case of copper(II) complexes one broad absorption band is observed $\sim 13.8 - 14.3$ k.k. region suggesting a distorted octahedral configuration. Basing on analytical and spectral data zinc(II) complexes have also an octahedral environment around the metal ion.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to University Grants Commission, New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. P. K. PANDA and B. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem. (London)*, In press.
2. C. D. RAO and B. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, 39, 689.
3. P. K. PANDA and B. K. MOHAPATRA, *Indian J. Chem.* (communicated).
4. R. M. SILVERSTEIN and G. C. BASSLER, "Spectrometric identification of organic compounds", Wiley, New York, 1971.
5. J. REEDIJK, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1971, 5, 687.
6. J. R. FERRARO, "Low frequency vibration of inorganic and co-ordination compounds", Plenum Press, New York, 1971.
7. J. REEDIJK, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, 13, 219.
8. R. V. BIAGETTI, W. C. BOTTJER and H. M. HAENDLER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 379.
9. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to ligand fields", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1976.
10. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.